

CAUSES OF CRIMES RELATED TO RELIGIOUS EXTREMISM, CONDITIONS THAT ENABLE THEM AND DESCRIPTION OF THE OFFENDER

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7468355>

Annotation: *Through this article, you can learn about the concept, types, occurrence, development, spread of crimes and offenses related to extremism that are happening around the world, the dangers they pose to our country and other countries today, and ways to prevent them.*

Key words: *extremism, types of extremism, danger, missionary work, financing of extremism, religious extremism, extremist material, fanaticism, foreign ideas, fundamentalism, extremist ideas, radicalism.*

Introduction

At present, extremism has become one of the most pressing and global problems in the international dimension as dangerous manifestations of terrorism, human trafficking, illegal migration organized crime. Without a clear idea of determinants in criminology, it is impossible to predict the principles of development of this phenomenon and draw up a plan of work aimed at preventing. Based on the conclusions of Western scientists who have studied extremism and terrorism and the problems arising from it and the information provided in the media, it can be seen how dangerous and terrible extremism and terrorism are committed in the next decade. In the 70s of the last century, there was an increase in the commission of terrorist acts in European countries, and especially in countries such as Germany and Italy, while currently it is possible to include the states of Iraq, Pakistan, Avgonistan, Nigeria, Syria, Russia, France, Belgium, Great Britain, the USA, India, Germany andhokazo.

In cases like these, terrorists have widely used subversive methods, such as assaulting and evading the lives of mainly state and political figures, hostage-taking of people, carrying out detonations in public institutions and public places, attacking and capturing air and sea transport, massacring civilians (such as in states such as India, Sri Lanka), seeking to seize or fire nuclear devices.

Extremism and terrorism also led the people of Uzbekistan, terrorist acts in Tashkent on February 16, 1999, appeared in the Batkent region of the Kyrgyz Republic in August 1999, organized armed attacks in the

border districts of the Tashkent region of the Republic, in July 2000 a group of extremists illegally entered the Sariosiyo District of Surkhandarya region and committed subversive actions, in 2004, It is enough to cite as an example the criminal actions carried out in May 2005 to seize power in Andijan, as well as the assassination murders committed in 2009 in Tashkent, Surkhandarya and other regions in relation to prominent religious figures and law enforcement officers.

The terrorist acts committed on September 11, 2001 in the United States claimed the lives of more than six thousand innocent people, the bloodshed of innocent people as a result of the atrocities that the terrorist organization, now called ISIS, is committed in a number of countries, and the fact that they are forced to leave their homes where they live and leave

MOXOKAMA AND RESULTS

The widespread spread of terrorism dates back to the end of the twentieth century and began to cover issues of a political, social, territorial, national and international scale, very extensive territories. According to information, more than 500 terrorist organizations are currently operating in the world, and the number of terrorist acts committed by them is increasing every year. N.According to melenteva, in the last ten years, 14 thousand 934 extremists have committed terrorist acts in 112 countries of the world, the absolute majority of which are located in different regions of the Earth's surface, characterized by the presence of problems of a specific ethnic, religious or other form, such a conclusion is also made by Iraq, the western coast of Jordan, Colombia, Spain, Thailand, Afghanistan, India, Pakistan, Turkey, Israel, France, Nepal, Russia.

This in turn necessitates the need for mutual coordination of international cooperation in the fight against it due to the increasing number of extremist and terrorist acts in the world. But understanding the essence, content and features of extremism and terrorism in this regard creates the need for a solution to the issue of determining its definition¹. After all, with a different view of the concept of extremism and a different understanding of it, it leads to a much greater limitation of the possibilities of fighting extremism on a single goal. Therefore, it is advisable to study the fundamental nature of extremism and terrorism, which threaten the prospects of mankind, to conduct

¹ "Criminology". General part: textbook / I.Ismailov, Q.R. Abdurasulova, I.Yu. Fazilov; responsible editor Sh.T. Ikramov. - T.: Mia Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2015. - 272 b

an in-depth study of the socio-economic, political, legal and spiritual factors that are causing it, and to analyze it politically philosophically

The occurrence of extremism and terrorism can be inextricably linked with the following reasons:

1) Social, at the same time, the unresolved nature of national and religious problems, as well as not all such problems, but self-assessment in these social, national groups, seeing oneself as such, should be assessed taking into account their ideality, the vital importance of existing values in traditions, traditions. Sometimes these groups try to express their individuality and immutability.

True, there is no possibility of an immediate solution to problems with such groups, already as a result of which the interests of another group are harmed (for example, in national and racial conflicts);

2) extremist and terrorist actions in war and military conflicts remain part of military action (for example, the attacks of Chechen fighters on Russian cities outside their territory in 1995-1996). Similar guerrilla movements are also committed in a typical way to Terror-ISM, and in this, the military actions carried out by military units in motion to invade, in order to arouse fear among the population on the occupied land, are as follows;

3) the presence of states or groups capable of having a high material supply and culture from their specific and side or distant neighbors, demonstrating their political, economic and military power, or, on the basis of this, making different demands on other countries or groups to achieve their goals. There is no doubt that the dark and rich coexistence of such states creates the prejudice and invisibility of some states or social groups, and is perceived as an enemy, and it is observed that, although such states cannot be overcome, various strikes are inflicted against them. In this, spiritual views are ignored, and such an enemy is recognized as worthy of just such attention;

4) the provision of activities in such a direction as secret or semi-secret societies, including religious and sectant organizations and their messianic position and, on the basis of this, "unity", "the right doctrine for the salvation of man" or the desire to improve human life in general, as well as general kindness, justice and eternal preservation of the human soul. When such associations and their teachings are not accepted by states and the public, in this case they seek to exert legal

pressure in order to achieve their goals (in political, ideological, religious, mystical, Magian).;

5) the lack of resolution of the necessary economic and financial problems, including the absence of legislative grounds associated with them, as well as disputes in the distribution of property, the lack of protection of commercialists, financial practitioners and all such businessmen by law enforcement agencies. This in turn caused the representatives of these strata to cause terrorist acts in areas such as intimidation and liquidation of competitors. As an example of this, the possibility of the use of criminal commercial systems of organized crime and their services, which are currently occurring in Russia, in the implementation of economic terrorism, has been opened².

Along with these listed reasons, the following negative factors that cause extremism and terrorism should also be listed. These are:

1) the weakness of state power, its institutions and various branches, the lack of skills of law enforcement state bodies in ensuring the discovery and neutralization of extremists and terrorists, as well as the complete non-implementation of such as punishing criminals in order to identify and detain persons preparing terrorist acts being prepared and prevent murders and other negative vices that they may

The worst thing is that such individuals are not exactly punished. It should be noted that the failure of many terrorist acts in the commercial sphere is also considered an extremely negative situation³.

2) the implementation of support, provision for the activities of extremists by certain groups and the population. Without such assistance, there would be no need to carry out extremism in national and religious directions. If there is such support, then the system of strict punishment of criminals (death penalty or increased prison sentences) will face the opposition of supporters of similar extremists and terrorists and will lead to the formation of new extremist groups and the expansion of the ranks of existing ones.

This means that in such situations it is necessary to behave in a specific political way. That is, it is necessary to make non-traditional political

² "Criminology". General part: textbook / I.Ismailov, Q.R. Abdurasulova, I.Yu. Fazilov; responsible editor Sh.T. Ikramov. - T.: Mia Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2015. - 272 b

³ Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 14, 2018 No. 3528 PP-3528 "on the introduction of a qualitatively new system for maintaining public order, prevention of offenses and the fight against crime in the city of Tashkent".

decisions, discuss among themselves and make such side-clicks, of course, at the same time to weaken the positive attitude towards extremism and terrorism and to create a separation from it, sometimes it is also of great importance to reveal the true images of the leaders and reveal the negative nature of their main slogans in;

3) the presence of a group of persons who have professional skills in military affairs and are excluded from military service and cannot find their place. True, such individuals will not be able to forgive their hit on the ground, and will fall under the influence of extremists and terrorists, since they are financially needy. Such cases can be shown in Germany that after the first World War a huge number of individuals fell under the influence of Nazis, the last case from the Vietnam War in the United States, "Afghans" in the territories dominated by the Soviets, and the use of those discharged from the army in terrorist activities.

Particular attention should be paid to the fact that the listed cases are specific conditions for extremism and terrorism.

In the coverage of subsequent elements of the criminological description of crimes related to extremism and terrorism, we think that the conditions for committing a crime are appropriate to cover the place, time of committing a crime, the weapon used, the object of aggression, the territory and the hokazos.

The conditions for committing a crime are understood as objects, phenomena and processes that arise, exist and develop before and during the commission of a crime, including the time, place, weather conditions of committing an illegal act, other characteristics of the environment, the behavior of persons not directly related to the phenomenon, psychological connections between them, as well as other circumstances of objective

The specificity of the crime of extremism and terrorism is also determined by the fact that they relate to the type of long-term crimes. For this reason, we will try to analyze the elements that depend on the investigation of the criminal case. From the point of view of the place of commission of extremist and terrorist acts, the analysis showed that mainly these crimes are committed in large cities and regional centers—65.3%, rail transport, air transport – 27.9%, in small cities – 3-5%. Rural areas have hardly been observed to commit terrorist acts.

At the same time, 39.5% of extremist acts were committed in public places, 31.6% in administrative and industrial facilities, 22.3% in public transport facilities, and the rest in other places .

The following factors influence the youth of our country to fall under the influence of destructive ideas:

- troubled families;
- problems in educational institutions;
- harmful effects of the internet;
- migration;
- destructive forces;
- alcohol and drug addiction;
- suicidal;
- lectures and video rollers absorbing pornographic and extremist and terrorist ideas;
- (popular culture);
- localism;
- extremism and terrorism.

Based on the studies carried out today and the existing theory in the science of criminology, we study conditionally by analyzing the causes and conditions of offenses associated with extremism and terrorism into the following types:

1. Causes and conditions in the spiritual sphere;
2. Causes and conditions in the socio-economic sphere;
3. The reasons and conditions in the field of organizational management are among them.

1. To causes and conditions in the spiritual sphere:

The emergence of an ideological gap – that is, the fact that in the days of the former Union, religion is divided into beliefs, and after independence, unlimited freedoms are given to faith in religion and they are left out of control;

Indeed, after the independence of our republic, a period of radical changes began in the social, political, spiritual, economic spheres. However, after the decay of the scholar system based on the creed of Marxism – Leninism, an ideological gap arose. Because, for more than 70 years, religious beliefs, weakened, Islamic scholars were repressed. Islamic ideas promote peace, intolerance among different nations and religions. But the ideas of religious fundamentalism and eksterimizim (wahobism, hezbut-Tahrir, Hezbollah), which entered our Republic from the 80s of the last century, further expanded its activities in the 90s. The negative results of this activity manifested themselves in the tragic events that took place in the capital of our country, that is, on February 16, 1999.

Some internal and external turmoil, unable to see positive changes in our country, the peaceful life of our people, the improvement of its life day after day and striving for a bright future without fear of any difficulties, rained various slander against the leaders of our state, their rational policy, urged our people to distract from the right path, forcibly overthrow the constitutional system under the

This, in turn, not only negatively affected the operational situation in our republic, but also led to the fact that some of our spiritually poor citizens, especially young people, whose worldview has not yet formed, fall under the influence of these currents and behave treacherously towards their people, parents, brothers and sisters;

The low level of legal consciousness and legal culture of the population, that is, the shallow nature of their understanding of religious and secular knowledge;

By providing strong financial, political and ideological support, our ghanims have been able to masterfully use some of the difficulties inherent in the transition period at the present time, some of our organizational aspects to our youth for half a year, a year, through their ideas promoted by the destructive chalasavod mullavachchas. As a result of the spread of the ideology of religious fanatics in our society on an increasingly wide scale, our youth fell under the influence of these chalasavod mullas.

Therefore, we need to teach our youth, first of all, our national ideology, values and give secular knowledge⁴.

2. Causes and conditions in the socio-economic sphere:

In our country to this day, many residents have not been able to find a job worthy of them, they are not satisfied with their monthly salary with the availability of vacancies;

failure of the activities of responsible organizations, self-government bodies of citizens, labor exchanges and social adaptation centers to meet the requirements of today and the closure of enterprises, institutions and organizations;

the growth of prices and the formation in the minds of citizens of the concepts of the priority of material life over spiritual life;

Our scientists, in many criminological literature and articles in popular science journals, point to problems in the economic sphere, which are the main causes of crime, as unemployment and crime .

⁴ Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 14, 2018 No. 3528 PP-3528 "on the introduction of a qualitatively new system for maintaining public order, prevention of offenses and the fight against crime in the city of Tashkent".

3. Causes and conditions in the field of organizational management:

The fact that religious affairs committees did not control the activities of religious institutions to promote religion;

Failure to take the necessary measures in the Prevention of crimes related to religious extremism in time;

We must also mention that it is no exaggeration to say that crimes related to religious extremism will be the result, if not the final conclusion of terrorism.

The reasons for the activation of extremism and fundamentalism in social life in Uzbekistan are as follows:

- the need to fill the space that has arisen in spiritual life due to the erosion of communist ideology;
- persecution of religious and religious in the former Union state;
- increased sense of national identity in people and the search for one's own lineage in ethnic terms;
- changes in socio-political and economic life;
- the support of foreign countries by currents and sects in an extremist and fundamentalist spirit.

The spread of extremism and fundamentalism in Uzbekistan from the late 80s and early 90s posed a serious threat to socio-political stability and civil harmony.

Uzbekistan has chosen the evolutionary path of building a new society, that is, the mechanism of building a democratic society will be gradually, gradually introduced into life. Extremists in such a situation try to present themselves as devotees fighting for democracy. Their popular, attractive, but roaring and unfounded claims to justice can be followed blindly by certain groups, in particular our youth, whose life experience is not enough. The foundations of the National idea, created in order to prevent such risks, are aimed at creating immunity to creativity and the influence of destructive ideas on the strength of these strata of the population, including the construction of a great state.

Uzbekistan is a multi-confessional state. Currently, representatives of more than 130 nationalities and nationalities live together in our country, 16 religious organizations belonging to confessiona operate freely in 0 . Extremists try to create contradictions between the population of the regions of the country and the social strata on the signs of "real" and "false" religiosity. Differences in the signs of religiosity

can lead to harmony between nations, friendship of peoples in the region.

The enmity, which is likely to occur between religious denominations within the country, can create unpleasant perceptions of Uzbekistan, even among Muslim and Gentile States or their community, or push our country into a whirlwind of conflict.

Another of the characteristics of extremism is that it can decide in the social mind the misconception that religion is a universal means of solving all economic, political and international problems, as well as conflicts. In fact, the religious worldview is a component of a system of ideas that reflect such a being as secularism or atheism. Religion, in turn, can effectively cooperate with a secular state on the way to a nationwide cultural upsurge. As proof of our opinion, we can cite the example of the fact that during the reign of Amir Timur, The Islamic religion served as a tool for the jipsing of forces fighting for the creation of a centralized state, serving political stability, social harmony and progress.

We can see that extremism and fundamentalism ultimately focus on terrorism. In other words, terrorism is the last ring of the chain. That is, radicalism – fanaticism – extremism (fundamentalism in some cases) – terrorism.

The activity of religion on the path of social development is hampered by supporters of fundamentalism and fanaticism. If supporters of modernity and fundamentalism in religion cannot compromise among themselves in the interests of society and the state, the existing contradictions will come out of the confessional framework, acquire a social meaning. From then on, these conflicts become a threatening force⁵.

Blindly believing and encouraging the claims of extremism and fundamentalism is the worldview of those who do not want a life in which the principles of nostalgia and tolerance of the old times were a priority⁶.

About this, in particular, on the consequences of following inhuman convictions contrary to the needs and expectations of the peoples of our country, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan

⁵ Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 14, 2018 No. 3528 PP-3528 "on the introduction of a qualitatively new system for maintaining public order, prevention of offenses and the fight against crime in the city of Tashkent".

⁶ "Criminology". General part: textbook / I.Ismailov, Q.R. Abdurasulova, I.Yu. Fazilov; responsible editor Sh.T. Ikramov. - T.: Mia Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2015. - 272 b

Islam Karimov said: "We must understand that those who blindly follow the crowded, attractive, but energetic and unfounded claims of fundamentalists about justice remain slaves of the will of others. We must clearly understand that these claims will ultimately prevail not only in the mind, but also in the fate of such people, especially our youth should clearly imagine this. Defiance to such influential people can also turn into a personal tragedy. The slave mutelik, the person's falling into the complication of lack of freedom, the absolute limitation of freedom of thought, effort and initiative are the most severe consequences of this."

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is extremely important in our republic to appreciate the current peace and tranquility, interethnic harmony and mutual respect between different religious denominations, to respect the rules established by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and to observe them without deviation. What the consequences of religious and national conflicts can lead to today is another proof that the extremist and terrorist actions taking place in the Central Asia region and around the world, as well as the victims of innocent people, how many people cause a feeling of fear in their hearts and souls. We are witnessing the fact that religious fanaticism and the negative situations caused by it bring only calamity to the people. This was proved by the intrigues of groups in the Fergana Valley, who chose the paths of the "false predecessors", "Hezbut-editors". Following them, supporting malicious ones is tantamount to betrayal of the motherland.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. From the speech of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, New York City, September 19, 2017.
2. President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev from his speech at the SHXT meeting held in Samarkand on September 16-17, 2022.
3. Karimov I.A. Our peace and security depend on our strength, our solidarity and our firm will. T. 12. - T., 2004. – B. 169.

4. "Criminology". General part: textbook / I.Ismailov, Q.R. Abdurasulova, I.Yu. Fazilov; responsible editor Sh.T. Ikramov. - T.: Mia Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2015. - 272 b.

5. "Criminology". Special part: textbook / I.Ismailov, Q.R. Abdurasulova et al. - T.: Mia Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2015. - 744 b.

6. Zaripav Z., Ismailov I. "Criminology". General part: textbook. - T., 1996. - 230 b.

7. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 14, 2018 No. 3528 PP-3528 "on the introduction of a qualitatively new system for maintaining public order, prevention of offenses and the fight against crime in the city of Tashkent".

Ubaydullaev Sherzod Muzaffarovich

Its academic staff is an ambassador, a part of the detachment commander, major